
Equilibrium Studies of Sulfanilic Acid with Some Transition Metal Ions by pH Metry in Aqueous Media

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Abstract: The Protonation constant and Stability constants of complexes between selected metal ions Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Cr (III) and Sulfanilic acid ligand (SA) have been determined at room temperature 280 C in the aqueous solution using Calvin Bjerrum titrimetric method. Calculations were made by Microsoft Excel Programme. Utilization of simply available 1N NaNO₃ as an electrolyte and inexpensive HNO₃ as an acid are the significant features of the work. Order of stability of the ligand with the metal ions was found to be Cr (III) > Cu (II) > Ni (II) > Co (II) > Zn (II). Cr (III) with higher oxidation state was found to be more stable as compared to all other selected transition metals.

Keywords: Sulfanilic acid, Protonation constant, Stability constants, Calvin Bjerrum.

I. Introduction

The acid-base dissociation constant (pK_a) of a drug is a key physicochemical parameter affecting many biopharmaceutical characteristics. The common drugs are weak acids or bases, understanding of the dissociation constant in each case helps in understanding the ionic form a molecule will take across a range of pH values. The well recognized relationship between pK_a and PK (pharmokinetic characteristics) has also resulted in the requirement for pK_a values to be measured for regulatory compliance. Formulation procedures for optimizing drug delivery also benefit from the determination of the pK_a . Given the importance of this parameter to the drug industry, it follows that an ability to estimate or measure the pK_a , together with a knowledge of their distribution, will be of great benefit [1].

Sulfonamides were the first effective chemotherapeutic agents to be employed systematically for the prevention and cure of bacterial infections [2]. It has been reported that biological activity of sulfur containing ligands increases on complexation. First row transition metal complexes like Cu, Zn, Co have attracted attention due to their biological importance. Copper complexes of antiepileptic drug show good efficiency than parent drugs. Recently Fatima A.I. studied metal complexes of sulfamethoxazole, she reported good anticancer behaviour against human colon carcinoma cells and hepatocellular carcinoma cells [3]. Ananadkumaran et al reported antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant properties for Schiff's bases of the sulfanilamide complexes [4].

Sulfur containing ligands are widespread among coordination compounds and are important components of biological transition metal complexes which possess many application like diuretics, antiglucuma or antiepileptic drugs among others. Sulfanilic acid derivatives have considerable interest. However, little information is available on stability constant of SA ligand with transition metal ions. Considering the importance of SA in mind; in the present paper, an attempt has been made to study the stability constants of SA with Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Cr (III)

metal ions. The titrations were carried out using Calvin-Bjerrum titrations technique at 28 °C temperature in the aqueous solution.

Materials And Methods

Ligand along with all the chemicals were obtained from SD fine AR grade. Metal nitrates were used due to their high solubility. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. NaOH solution was standardised using oxalic acid solution.

Procedure

The experimental procedure involved titration of Acid, Acid+ Ligand, Acid+ ligand+ Metal ions against standard NaOH solution.

1. HNO₃ (5ml) + NaNO₃(5ml)
2. HNO₃ (5ml) + NaNO₃ (5ml) + ligand (10ml)
3. HNO₃ (5ml) + NaNO₃ (5ml) + ligand (10ml) + Metal ion(3ml)

A standard sodium hydroxide solution was employed to titrate the sample using the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique. All solutions were prepared using double glass distilled water and maintained at a constant ionic strength by adding sodium nitrate (NaNO₃). Titrations were conducted in distilled water, with pH readings recorded for every 0.02 ml increment of NaOH added. The resulting pH versus volume of NaOH curves was analyzed using the Calvin Bjerrum titrimetric method and a Microsoft Excel program to determine the proton-ligand constants. All measurements were conducted at room temperature using an ELICO digital pH meter equipped with a magnetic stirrer and a combined glass electrode assembly was employed for pH determinations. The pH meter was calibrated before each titration using aqueous standard buffer solutions of pH 7.00, 4.00 and 10 prepared from buffer tablets. The instrument exhibited a sensitivity of 0.01 pH units and a measurement range of 0.00 to 14.00 pH with a resolution of 0.005 pH units. The pH meter was switched on for at least 30 minutes before measurements to ensure stability. Glass electrodes were stored in appropriate storage solutions when not in use and were rinsed thoroughly with distilled water before each measurement.

Results And Discussion

Table 1. Protonation constant and Stability constant of SA with metal ions

pK ₂	Metals	Log K
Half integral	Cr	4.6462
3.4578	Cu	4.3279
	Ni	4.2979
	Co	4.2718
Point wise	Zn	4.0673
3.4577		

Data obtained from titrimetric analysis was used for determining Protonation constant (pK) and stability constant. SA has two binding groups, amine group and Sulphonic acid group. But amino groups are not free to bind. Unlike simple amine –NH₂ group of SA is not free to react with acid; Protonation of amino group is already accounted with zwitter ion. Therefore, pK₁ value was not found; pK₂ value of 3.4578 is reported. pK₂ values obtained by Half integer method and point wise method were found to be in agreement. The stability constant values suggest moderate level of the stability of the complexes. SA has a single amino group and sulphonic acid group, which can act as binding sites, it does not have multiple chelating groups like other well-known chelating agents, therefore stability constant for SA chelates are lower as compared to other agents like EDTA, indicating weak binding for metal ions. The order of stability of the complexes was found to be Cr (III) > Cu (II) > Ni (II) > Co (II) > Zn (II). Cr (III) with higher oxidation state is more stable as compared to all other selected transition metals. Higher stability of Cr indicates that complex is more stable compared to rest of the metal ions.

Figure 1: Calculation of pK_2 by half integer method

Figure 2: Metal ligand formation curve for SA and Zinc metal ion

Conclusion

Formation of binary complexes of Sulfanilic acid has been confirmed with transition metal ions pH metrically. Order of stability of the ligand with the metal ions was found to be Cr (III) > Cu (II) > Ni (II) > Co (II) > Zn(II). Formation of 1: 1 complexes has been reported. These complexes may improve its application in drug industry. This would require specially designed research conducted by specialized drug chemist.

References

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